

Fungicidal Activities and Mass Spectral Studies of Some Schiff Bases Derived from *para*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde and Their Derivatives

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A new series of Schiff bases derived from 4-substituted, 4,5-disubstituted-2-aminothiazoles, substituted-2-aminobenzothiazoles and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde was synthesised. Condensation of the Schiff bases with chloroacetylchloride and subsequent reaction with piperidine and morpholine yielded corresponding acetoxy derivatives. Cycloaddition of the Schiff bases with thioglycolic acid yielded thiazolidinone derivatives. The compounds were characterised by elemental analysis, ir and mass spectra and screened for their fungicidal activity.

It has been observed that the biological activity of certain organic compounds is related to their ability for complex formation with metal ions¹. Many of the anticancer drugs are also viable ligands². The importance of thiazole and benzothiazole derivatives, and Schiff bases as biologically active compounds are well known. Schiff base complexes have been suggested as models for enzymes such as galactose oxidase³. All these observations and the essential role of azomethin linkage in certain biological reactions prompted us to synthesise some Schiff bases having thiazole nucleus. These Schiff bases, prepared by the condensation of 2-aminothiazoles and 2-aminobenzothiazoles with salicylaldehyde, 5-bromo and 3,5-dibromo salicylaldehydes were also found to be very good ligands^{4,5}. In the present communication, we report the synthesis and fungicidal activity of some new thiazole and benzothiazole Schiff bases which differ considerably from the above Schiff bases as regards to their chelating ability.

The Schiff bases were prepared by condensation of the corresponding aldehydes with substituted 2-aminothiazoles and benzothiazoles. Condensation of these Schiff bases with chloroacetyl chloride yielded the corresponding chloroacetyl derivatives which on further reaction with morpholine and piperidine formed the corresponding morpholino and piperidino acetoxy compounds. Cycloaddition of the Schiff bases with thioglycolic acid gave the corresponding thiazolidinone derivatives.

The structure of the Schiff bases was elucidated on the basis of elemental analysis, ir and mass spectra. The ir spectra of Schiff bases showed a sharp band around 3450 cm⁻¹ and a broad medium band around 3100 cm⁻¹ (free and bonded -OH) and a strong sharp band in the region 1640-1625 cm⁻¹ (C=N). On thiazolidinone formation, the band due to C=N stretching is lost and a strong tertiary amide stretch (N-C=O) is observed around 1680 cm⁻¹. Disappearance of the OH band

Scheme 1

and appearance of a new band around 1715-1725 cm⁻¹ established the formation of acetoxy derivatives.

The main mass spectral fragmentation pattern of the Schiff bases derived from 4-aryl- and 4,5-diaryl-

thiazoles is similar to that of the Schiff bases reported earlier⁴. All of them give stable molecular ions (base peak in most cases) and (M-1)⁺ peaks. Other characteristic fragments observed were formed by the loss of CO, SH and HCN radicals. The (M-CH=S) and (M-OH) peaks observed in earlier Schiff bases are not observed in the present series. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of one representative member of the series of Schiff bases derived from 2-aminobenzothiazoles (4, R=H) is depicted in Scheme 1. Surprisingly, the percentage of molecular ion peak and (M-1) peak is much low in comparison to other Schiff bases. The main fragmentation process involves rupture of 1,9 and 3,8, 1,9 and 2,3, 1,2 and 3,8, and 1,2 and 2,3 bonds of the benzothiazole nucleus⁶⁻⁷. Other characteristic fragments observed were due to the loss of CHO, CH₂O, (CH₂O+C₂H₂) radicals from the molecular ion. Most of the fragmentation patterns were supported by the appearance of appropriate metastable peaks.

Experimental

Melting-points were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. IR spectra were determined in Perkin-Elmer 337 grating infrared spectrophotometer in nujol mull. Mass spectra were recorded on a varian MAT SM 1-BH mass spectrophotometer at 70 ev at C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

4-Aryl-2-aminothiazoles were prepared by the condensation of substituted acetophenone with thiourea in presence of iodine⁸ and 4,5-diaryl-2-aminothiazoles were prepared from their respective desyl chloride⁹ and thiourea. Substituted 2-amino-benzothiazoles were prepared from the respective thioureas¹⁰.

4',5'-Diphenylthiazole-2'-imino-(4-hydroxy)-benzylidene (1, R₁=R₂=C₆H₅): A mixture of 2-amino-4,5-diphenylthiazole (0.01 mol), *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) and piperidine (3-4 drops) was refluxed for 1.5 h on a water bath. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the solid separated was filtered and crystallised from ethanol (75%), m.p. 201° (Found: C, 74.00; H, 4.20; N,

7.50. C₂₂H₁₆N₂OS requires C, 74.15; H, 4.50; N, 7.86%). In a similar way, other substituted thiazole/benzothiazole-imino-(4-hydroxy)-benzylidenes were prepared. Melting point, yield and antifungal activity are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—SCHIFF BASES (1)*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p. °C	% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 500 ppm
1.	C ₆ H ₅	H	110	81.5
2.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	150	84.6
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	195	87.2
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	203	87.8
5.	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄	H	221	88.1
6.	α -Naphthyl	H	238	89.1
7.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	201	82.3
8.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	150	87.8
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	120	88.9

* Elemental analyses (C, H, N) within $\pm 0.5\%$ of theoretical values. Yields between 60-75%.

TABLE 2—SCHIFF BASES (4)*

Sl. no.	R'	M.p. °C	% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 500 ppm
1.	H	185	80.5
2.	6-Cl	188	85.4
3.	6-CH ₃	240	82.3
4.	6-OCH ₃	198	84.7
5.	4-CH ₃	160	81.6

* Elemental analyses (C, H, N) within $\pm 0.5\%$ of theoretical values. Yields between 55-70%.

4',5'-Diphenylthiazole-2'-imino-(4-chloroacetoxy)-benzylidene (2, R=Cl, R₁=R₂=C₆H₅): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), chloroacetyl chloride (0.015 mol) in dry benzene (15-20 ml) and pyridine (2-3 drops) was refluxed for 5 h on water bath. After reflux, the excess of benzene and pyridine were removed under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was washed thoroughly with water and crystallised from ethanol (65%), m.p. 115° (Found: N, 5.15; Cl, 7.59. C₂₄H₁₇O₂SCl requires N, 5.39; Cl, 7.86%). Other substituted thiazole/benzothiazole-imino-(4-chloroacetoxy)-benzylidenes were prepared similarly.

4',5'-Diphenylthiazole-2'-imino-(4-morpholinoacetoxy)-benzylidene (2, R=morpholinyl, R₁=R₂=C₆H₅): A mixture of 4',5'-diphenylthiazole-2'-imino-(4-chloroacetoxy)-benzylidene (2, R=Cl, R₁=R₂=C₆H₅) (0.005 mol) and morpholine (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 8 h on water bath. After reflux, excess of benzene was removed under reduced pressure. The solid mass, then obtained was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol (60%), m.p. 188° (Found: C, 66.6; H, 4.80; N, 8.55. C₂₈H₂₅N₃O₃S requires C, 70.15; H, 4.60; N, 8.77%). In a similar way, other substituted thiazole/benzothiazole-imino-(4-morpholino/piperidino acetoxy)benzylidenes were prepared.

Melting point, yield and antifungal activity are given in Tables 3 and 4.

yield and antifungal activity are given in Tables 5 and 6.

TABLE 3—ACETOXY SCHIFF BASES (2)*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p. °C	% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 500 ppm
R=morpholinyl				
1.	C ₆ H ₅	H	105	69.5
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	118	71.8
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	160	75.4
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	130	76.5
5.	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄	H	185	74.2
6.	α -Naphthyl	H	215	79.8
7.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	188	72.5
8.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	121	74.9
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	110	76.9
R=Piperidine				
10.	C ₆ H ₅	H	103	69.8
11.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	106	72.0
12.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	152	75.6
13.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	125	76.8
14.	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄	H	162	74.5
15.	α -Naphthyl	H	200	80.1
16.	C ₆ H ₅	O ₂ C ₆ H ₄	115	72.8
17.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	95	74.9
18.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	105	76.9

* Elemental analyses (C, H, N) within $\pm 0.5\%$ of theoretical values. Yields between 50-65%.

TABLE 4—ACETOXY SCHIFF BASES (5)*

Sl. no.	R'	M.p. °C	% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 500 ppm
R=morpholinyl			
1.	H	187	70.4
2.	6-Cl	152	75.1
3.	6-CH ₃	110	71.5
4.	6-OCH ₃	198	74.6
5.	4-OH ₂	170	72.1
R=Piperidine			
6.	H	115	70.6
7.	6-Cl	105	75.4
8.	6-CH ₃	95	72.3
9.	6-OCH ₃	125	74.9
10.	4-OH ₂	140	72.5

* Elemental analyses (C, H, N) within $\pm 0.5\%$ of theoretical values. Yields between 50-60%.

2-(4'-Hydroxyphenyl)-3-(4'', 5''-diphenyl-thiazol-2''-yl)-4-thiazolidinone (3, R₁=R₂=C₆H₅): A mixture of 4',5'-diphenylthiazole-2'-imino-(4-hydroxy)-benzylidene (1, R₁=R₂=C₆H₅) (0.01 mol), thioglycolic acid (0.015 mol) in dry benzene (30 ml) was refluxed for 6 h on water bath. After reflux, the reaction mixture was cooled and excess of benzene was removed under reduced pressure. The solid, thus obtained, was washed several times with NaHCO₃ solution and water and finally crystallised from ethanol (65%), m.p. 161° (Found: C, 55.50; H, 4.66; N, 6.12. C₂₂H₁₈N₂O₂S₂ requires C, 66.67; H, 4.17; N, 6.48%). In a similar way, other thiazolidinones of the series were prepared. Melting point,

TABLE 5—THIAZOLIDINONES (3)*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p. °C	% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 500 ppm
1.	C ₆ H ₅	H	160	56.1
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	184	56.2
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	155	61.5
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	165	61.8
5.	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄	H	190	59.5
6.	α -Naphthyl	H	>250	62.3
7.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	161	57.2
8.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	139	59.5
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	112	61.5

* Elemental analyses (C, H, N) within $\pm 0.5\%$ of theoretical values. Yields between 55-60%.

TABLE 6—THIAZOLIDINONES (6)*

Sl. no.	R'	M.p. °C	% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 500 ppm
1.	H	170	55.8
2.	6-Cl	184	62.7
3.	6-CH ₃	218	59.4
4.	6-OCH ₃	198	60.5
5.	6-OH ₂	210	59.6

* Elemental analyses (C, H, N) within $\pm 0.5\%$ of theoretical values. Yields between 50-55%.

Fungicidal activity: For fungicidal assay poisoned food technique was used¹¹. All the compounds were tested for their toxicity towards *Curvularia* species at a concentration of 500 ppm. The experiments were performed in duplicate and the average inhibition is reported. The percentage inhibition was calculated by the following expression.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = (1 - X/Y) \times 100$$

where X=weight of the growth of colony in test sample, and Y=weight of the growth of colony in the control sample.

The percentage inhibition of the germination of conidi of the above test fungus during 48 h is given in Tables 1-6. A few generalisation regarding the structure-activity relationship has been made. Among the compounds screened, the Schiff bases were the most active. But they are less active than the corresponding Schiff bases derived from 4-aryl-2-aminothiazoles and salicylaldehyde/5-bromo and 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde⁴. The presence of halogen, naphthyl and methoxy groups in the compound enhances the fungicidal activity. It is also observed that the Schiff bases are more active than the corresponding thiazolidinones and acetoxy derivatives.

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